

Clinico Pathological Assessment of Non Palpable Axillary Lymph Nodes in Early Breast CancerKarthik G B¹, J T Basavaraj², Harshith Hegde³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, SS Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Davangere²Professor, Department of General Surgery, JJM Medical College, Davangere³Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, JJM Medical College, Davangere

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Abstract:**Background:** Axillary lymph node status is a significant prognostic pathological factor in patients with operable primary breast cancer. Axillary staging allows loco-regional control and provides relevant information to direct adjuvant systemic therapy.**Methods:** 30 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria were prospectively studied. Clinico pathological characteristics were assessed and the performance of AUS and AUS guided biopsy for staging the axilla was summarized using sensitivities and specificities, treating the final histopathologic findings as the true status ascertaining the presence or absence of nodal metastases.**Results:** The mean age of study participants was 47.8yrs, the mean duration of tumour was 3.2 months and the mean size of tumour was 3.25cm. 46.7% of the patients had lump in the upper outer quadrant. On postoperative histopathological examination, 27 patients had invasive ductal carcinoma – not otherwise specified and 14 patients had metastasis in 1-3 ipsilateral axillary lymph nodes. The sensitivity and specificity of AUS was 64.7% and 84.6% respectively and the sensitivity and specificity of AUS guided FNAC was 82.3% and 100% respectively.**Conclusions:** In our study, tumour size, quadrant and duration significantly affected the status of axillary nodal metastasis but not the age, menopausal status, family history and breastfeeding. AUS guided FNAC is highly specific for assessing nodal metastasis, plays a role in sparing SLNB in early breast cancer and in triaging cases for adjuvant systemic therapy. Our results support the routine use of AUS and AUS guided FNAC for preoperative evaluation in early breast cancer.**Keywords:** Early breast cancer, clinically non palpable lymph nodes, Axillary ultrasonography, Axillary ultrasound guided FNAC.

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Introduction

In Indian women, breast cancer is the second most common cause of death due to cancer next to carcinoma cervix. It is reported that one in 22 women in India is likely to suffer from breast cancer during their lifetime [1]. The rise is being documented mainly in the metros but many in the rural India go unnoticed. The relatively constant mortality despite increase in incidence of the disease may be the result of improved outcome secondary to earlier detection and advances in treatment modalities.

The importance of management of breast cancer itself is to provide loco-regional control of the primary tumour and to reduce any potential for metastasis to distant sites. Axillary lymph node status is a significant prognostic pathological factor in patients with operable primary breast cancer. It

remains the most powerful predictor of recurrence and survival. Axillary dissection has remained for years the standard technique for the majority of cases.

This study is an attempt at earlier detection of axillary nodal metastases in patients of early breast cancer with clinically non palpable lymph nodes which helps in accurate clinical staging, need for further axillary clearance and other modalities of treatment like chemotherapy and radiotherapy.

Materials and Methods**Method of data collection:** This was a prospective observational study conducted with sample size of 30 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria over a duration of 24 months.

Objectives:

- To study the role of preoperative axillary ultrasonography (AUS) and USG guided FNAC in detecting clinically negative nodal metastases.
- To correlate the findings of AUS guided FNAC with post-operative histopathological diagnosis.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients admitted to the surgery wards with the diagnosis of early breast cancer with clinically non palpable axillary lymph nodes.

Exclusion Criteria:

- All pregnant women
- Patients who have clinically palpable lymph nodes in the axilla
- Patient above 80 years of age who were not operated on
- Recurrent breast lump in a previously operated patient

Methodology

Patients who were diagnosed to have early breast cancer with clinically non-palpable axillary lymph nodes underwent preoperative axillary ultrasonography (AUS) and ultrasound guided FNAC of lymph nodes.

AUS was performed using a standard 5 to 13 MHz linear array transducer. AUS was performed prospectively by dedicated breast imaging radiologists, most often at the time of ultrasound examination of the primary tumour, before a tissue diagnosis of the primary lesion was performed. Axillary lymph nodes were determined to be either normal in appearance or suspicious in appearance. Suspicious lymph nodes were identified based on standard morphologic criteria including generalized or focal thickening of the cortex, hypoechoic node, rounded appearance and effacement of the lymph node fatty hilum.

AUS guided FNAC was performed in all the cases irrespective of whether AUS determined the nodes to be normal or suspicious for malignancy. FNAC was performed manually using a 23-gauge needle attached to a 10-mL syringe, after administration of superficial local anaesthesia with 1% Xylocaine. FNAC was performed under ultrasound guidance with direct visualization of the needle entering the cortex of the lymph node to confirm position of the needle tip in the appropriate location and on average 3 passes were made. Aspirates were prepared with standard Giemsa and Papanicolaou staining and examined by a dedicated

cytopathologist. Cytology was classified as positive or negative for malignancy.

All patients underwent surgery in the form of simple mastectomy/lumpectomy and axillary lymph node dissection. Post-operatively axillary lymph node assessment was done through histopathological examination.

Clinico pathological characteristics evaluated included patient age, menopausal status, family history, breastfeeding, tumour size, tumour location, tumour histology, overall pathologic stage, type of surgical therapy and final histopathology findings.

The performance of AUS and AUS guided biopsy for staging the axilla was summarized using sensitivities and specificities, treating the final histopathologic findings as the true status ascertaining the presence or absence of nodal metastases. Similar summary statistics also were calculated within subgroups determined by clinico pathological factors like patient age, menopausal status, tumour location, tumour size, tumour histology.

Results

In the present study, 40% of the patients were in the age group of 34-44. The youngest patient was 34years and the oldest patient was 65years. 17 patients had lump in the right breast and 13 patients had lump in the left breast. Majority (46.7%) of the patients had lump in the upper outer quadrant and the least in the lower inner quadrant (6.7%). 17 patients were postmenopausal and 13 patients had not attained menopause. 2 patients (6.7%) had family history of breast cancer. 2 patients (6.7%) were nulliparous and 16 patients (53.4%) had 3-5 children. there was no history of breastfeeding in 3 patients (10%). most of the patients i.e. 24(80%) were diagnosed clinically to have TNM stage IIa disease and 6 patients had stage I disease. 26(86.7%) patients underwent surgery in the form of simple mastectomy and axillary lymph node dissection and 4(13.3%) patients underwent lumpectomy and axillary lymph node dissection. 14(46.7%) patients had metastasis in 1-3 ipsilateral axillary lymph nodes, 13(43.3%) patients had no metastasis and 3(10%) patients had micro metastasis in axillary lymph nodes. On postoperative histopathological examination, 27 (90%) patients had invasive ductal carcinoma – not otherwise specified.

Table 1: Comparison of study participants based on their mean age, duration of tumour and size of tumour with the status of post-operative nodal metastasis.

Sl. no	Characteristics	Positive nodal metastasis (N=17) Mean (SD)	Negative nodal metastasis (N=13) Mean (SD)	t value, Degrees of freedom	p value#
1	Age in years	49.1 (9.2)	46 (9)	0.90, 28	0.37
2	Duration in months	4.1 (1.5)	2 (1)	4.48, 28	0.001*
3	Size in cm	3.93 (0.6)	2.37 (0.8)	5.75, 28	0.001*

Note: # p value based on student's t test, * indicated statistically significant p value (<0.05), figure within parenthesis indicates standard deviation.

In the present study, size of the tumour and duration of the tumour significantly affected the status of nodal metastasis but not the age of the study participant.

Table 2: Association and agreement between pre-operative USG examination of axillary lymph node and post-operative histopathology report of study participants. (N=30)

Nodal metastasis		Post-Op HPR		Total	Chi-square value, df	p value#	Kappa value	p value@
		Positive	Negative					
Pre-Op	Positive	11	2	13	7.298, 1	0.007*	0.47	0.007*
AUS	Negative	6	11	17				
Total		17	13	30				

NOTE: # p value based on Chi-square test, @ p value based on Kappa statistics. * Statistically significant p value (<0.05), df- degrees of freedom

In the present study, there is significant association between pre-operative USG examination of axillary lymph node and post-operative histopathology report of study participants.

Table 3: Association and agreement between pre-operative USG- FNAC of axillary lymph node and post-operative histopathology report of study participants. N=30.

Nodal metastasis		Post-Op HPR		Total	Chi-square value, df	P value#	Kappa value	P value@
		Positive	Negative					
AUS	Positive	14	0	14	20.07. 1	0.001*	0.80	0.001*
FNAC	Negative	3	13	16				
Total		17	13	30				

Note: AUS FNAC - Axillary ultrasound guided fine needle, # p value based on Chi-square test, @ p value based on Kappa statistics. * Statistically significant p value (<0.05), df- degrees of freedom.

In the present study, there is significant association between pre-operative USG- FNAC of axillary lymph node and post-operative histopathology report of study participants.

Table 4: Interpretation of Kappa

Value of K	Strength of agreement
< 0.20	Poor
0.21 - 0.40	Fair
0.41 - 0.60	Moderate
0.61 - 0.80	Good
0.81 - 1.00	Very good

The K value can be interpreted as follows (Altman, 1991) [2]:

Table 5: Calculated sensitivity and specificity

Sl.no	Indices of screening test	AUS (95% CI)	AUS FNAC (95% CI)
1	Sensitivity	64.7 (54.8 – 74.2)	82.3 (73 – 88.9)
2	Specificity	84.6 (76.4 – 91.3)	100 (96.3 - 100)
3	Positive predictive value	84.6 (76.4 – 91.3)	100 (76.4 – 91.3)
4	Negative predictive value	64.7 (53.7- 73.3)	81.2 (71.9 – 88.1)

Note: AUS FNAC - Axillary ultrasound guided fine needle aspiration cytology, AUS - Axillary ultrasonography, 95% CI- 95% Confidence interval.

In the present study, the sensitivity and specificity of AUS is 64.7%.

And 84.6% respectively and the sensitivity and specificity of AUS FNAC is 82.3% and 100% respectively.

Statistical analysis:

1. Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analysed using software SPSS version 24.0.
2. Description of study variables were done using proportions for categorical variables like age category, parity etc., and in mean and standard deviation for continuous variables like duration of tumour and tumour size.
3. Association of age category, parity, and other features with post-operative histopathology finding of nodal metastasis were done using chi square test.
4. Mean duration of tumour and size of tumour were compared between nodal metastasis positive and negative group of study participants using student's t test.

5. Agreement between pre-operative lymph node metastasis with post-operative histology report was carried out using kappa statistics.
6. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value were calculated for preoperative lymph node examination using ultrasonography to detect non clinical nodal involvement and reported with their 95% confidence interval.
7. All statistical tests were two tailed and were considered significant when the p value is less than 0.05.

Discussion

The presence of axillary lymph node metastases in breast cancer is an important factor in assessing prognosis and determines management after surgery [3]. Physical examination of the axilla alone can be inaccurate in identifying lymph nodes involved with metastatic disease. The false negative rate of physical examination alone has been reported to be as high as 30% to 45%. [4]

Table 6: Sensitivity and Specificity of AUS in various studies

Study	TP	TN	FP	FN	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Present study	11	11	2	6	64.7	84.6
Yang et al. [5]	22	53	1	7	75.9	98.1
Bonnema et al. [4]	22	84	4	40	35	95.5
Deurloo et al. [6]	48	130	17	72	40.5	88.4
Bedrosian et al. [7]	14	141	14	39	26.4	91.0

Table 7: Sensitivity and Specificity of AUS guided FNAC in various studies

Study	TP	TN	FP	FN	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Present study	14	13	0	3	82.3	100
Bonnema et al. [4]	39	32	0	10	79.5	100
De kanter et al. [8]	93	119	0	5	94.9	100
Krishnamurthy et al. [10]	67	24	0	12	84.8	100
Sapino et al. [9]	49	35	0	11	81.6	100

In the present study, p value is 0.001(<0.05) and hence there is a significant association between pre-operative USG examination of axillary lymph node and post-operative histopathology report of study participants.

Evaluation of the axilla by sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is an accurate, less invasive alternative to axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) and it has become the standard of care in patients with clinically node-negative breast cancer. [11] Although SLNB is clearly less invasive than ALND, SLNB is not without morbidity and anaesthetic risk. It has been found that 1–15% of patients with a negative SLNB for metastases have other affected lymph nodes in the same region. [12] In addition, SLNB often is performed as a staged procedure, requiring that breast cancer patients undergo 2 or more surgeries for definitive staging and treatment of the axilla.

Axillary ultrasound (AUS) is a potentially valuable technique for identifying axillary metastases. [13] AUS permits the visualization of lymph node size, shape, contour, and changes in cortical morphology and texture that appear to be associated with the presence of axillary metastases. However, sonographic signs of metastatic disease sometimes overlap with those of benign reactive changes, limiting the ability of this modality alone to accurately stage the axilla. The addition of FNAC has been shown to increase the specificity of nodal staging [14–18] Patients with positive AUS guided FNAC can be spared a SLNB procedure and staged treatment of the axilla which may result in decreased time to adjuvant therapies.

Negative sonographic results do not exclude axillary lymph node metastases. Factors that contribute to discordance between preoperative AUS guided FNAC and final histopathology

include sampling error in lymph nodes with less than 5-mm metastatic deposits.

The remaining patients with sonographically negative axillae would be candidates for SLNB, improving the negative predictive value of the sentinel node biopsy because of the lower prevalence of metastases and thereby increasing the certainty of that technique.

Conclusion

Our study has demonstrated a significant effect of tumour size, tumour quadrant and duration of the tumour on the involvement of axillary lymph nodes in early breast cancer. Age of the patient, menopausal status, family history, and breastfeeding and tumour histology did not have significant association with axillary nodal metastasis in our study.

Axillary sonography is moderately sensitive and fairly specific in the diagnosis of axillary metastatic involvement. USG guided biopsy of the sonographically suspicious nodes increases the specificity which reaches 100%. The relatively lower sensitivity and higher specificity of AUS observed in the present study and most other series suggests that although AUS is unlikely to lead to a high false-positive rate, it does not have the diagnostic power to identify all involved metastatic lymph nodes as a screening tool. AUS alone is not definitive for axillary staging and a tissue diagnosis is essential to determine the presence of metastatic lymph node disease.

AUS combined with FNAC represents a minimally invasive procedure that can accurately stage the axilla, avoid staged surgical procedures and allow for definitive treatment planning in patients with early breast cancer with clinically non palpable axillary lymph nodes. When AUS was combined with FNAC, we observed an improved sensitivity of 82.3% and a specificity of 100%. AUS and AUS guided FNAC of axillary lymph nodes is an excellent adjunct to the preoperative workup of all patients with clinically non palpable lymph nodes in early breast cancer.

Limitations of the study:

- Certain pathological factors like histological grade, ER and PR status were not analysed in this study.
- Lympho-vascular invasion closely associated with axillary lymph node positivity by tumour cells could not be analysed in our patients.
- Patients had to be referred to another centre for radiotherapy as the facility was not available within the institute and hence follow up could not be studied effectively.

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